

THE UNREST

RMN NEWS MAGAZINE ON ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL UPHEAVALS IN THE WORLD

‘वोट चोर गद्दी छोड़’ रैली

Protest Against Election Theft in India

AN EDITORIAL INITIATIVE OF RAMAN MEDIA NETWORK (RMN)

EDITOR: RAKESH RAMAN
WWW.RMNNEWS.COM

Photo: Congress

‘Vote Chor Gaddi Chhod’ Rally

Rahul Gandhi reiterated his familiar rhetoric against what he described as the “Narendra Modi–RSS government,” vowing to remove the regime from power. [Read More](#)

Ukraine’s Defense

NATO Allies and partners have pledged more than 4 billion dollars for Ukraine under the NATO’s Prioritised Ukraine Requirements List (PURL) initiative. [Read More](#)

Adani Bribery Case

The legal pursuit by the US Securities and Exchange Commission against Gautam and Sagar Adani has entered its second year with no progress. [Read More](#)

Bollywood’s Dual Crisis

Bollywood is currently navigating a severe credibility crisis driven by widespread manipulation and artificial buzz within the film industry. [Read More](#)

Delhi-NCR Confirms Winter Smog Emergency

The Delhi-NCR region is grappling with a severe public health emergency, having experienced one of the most polluted months in recent years during November 2025. All 10 of India’s most polluted cities were located in the Delhi-NCR region. [Read More](#)

EVM Manipulation in India

A fresh political storm has erupted in India as Congress MP Rahul Gandhi accused the Modi government of evading questions on electoral integrity. [Read More](#)

Trump Launches 'Gold Card'

President Trump has launched the "Trump Gold Card," a new immigration initiative designed to provide a direct path to citizenship for qualified individuals. [Read More](#)

Umar Khalid Granted Interim Bail

The situation of Khalid is being contrasted with BJP leader Kapil Mishra, who is considered a main accused in the Delhi riots and is enjoying state impunity. [Read More](#)

CIVICUS and Asia Centre Case

My recent experience with CIVICUS and the Asia Centre raises troubling questions about the responsibility they bear when engaging with journalists. [Read More](#)

International Claims Commission for Ukraine

Leaders and senior politicians from across Europe and beyond are preparing to gather at the World Forum in The Hague on Tuesday, December 16, to launch a new convention establishing the International Claims Commission for Ukraine. [Read More](#)

Acknowledging Hate Speech in India: Karnataka's Landmark Bill

<p>THE PROBLEM: India's Legal Gap on Hate Speech</p> <p>"Hate Speech" Is Legally Undefined</p> <p>Existing Laws Are A Poor Fit</p> <p>India's criminal laws lack a formal definition, forcing reliance on other provisions.</p> <p>Agencies use general laws meant for "public order," not specifically for hate speech.</p> <p>Only a 20.2% Conviction Rate</p> <p>Data from 2020 shows convictions are rare under the most frequently used existing law.</p>	<p>THE SOLUTION: Karnataka's Proposed Bill</p> <p>A First-of-its-Kind State Law</p> <p>Expands Protected Categories</p> <p>The bill specifically defines and criminalizes hate speech and hate crimes.</p> <p>Includes protections for gender and sexual orientation, beyond traditional classifications.</p> <p>Introduces "Collective Liability"</p> <p>Holds organisations and their leaders responsible for hate speech linked to them.</p>
--	--

Hate Speech in India

The legal landscape concerning hate speech in India, focusing on the proposed Karnataka Hate Speech and Hate Crimes (Prevention) Bill, 2025. [Read More](#)

Telangana Startup Fund

For Telangana's entrepreneurial landscape, CM A. Revanth Reddy has introduced a ₹1,000 crore fund aimed at fueling the growth of startups in the state. [Read More](#)

Microsoft Investment in India

Satya Nadella announced Microsoft's largest-ever investment in Asia, committing over US\$ 17.5 billion for developing AI capabilities in India. [Read More](#)

China Anti-Corruption Move

China executed Bai Tianhui, the former general manager of China Huarong International Holdings (CHIH), after he was found guilty of corruption. [Read More](#)

DPIIT Proposes Hybrid AI Copyright Model

The Department of Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade (DPIIT) published its working paper examining the intersection of generative artificial intelligence (AI) and copyright law. This paper compiles the recommendations of an eight-member Committee. [Read More](#)

European Film Market 2026 Announces Major Program Expansion

The European Film Market, scheduled for February 12 to 18, 2026, launches its new edition as a key component of the 76th Berlinale. The market features an expanded program, new strategic partnerships, and a continued emphasis on cross-sector collaboration. [Read More](#)

Global Transmedia Science-Fiction Project

Robojit and the Sand Planet, a science-fiction property originally conceived as a novel, is being developed as a global transmedia project encompassing film, animation, graphic storytelling, and interactive formats. [Read More](#)

Trump Targets Netflix-Warner Bros. Mega-Deal

President Donald Trump has expressed concerns regarding the proposed multi-billion-dollar acquisition of Warner Bros. by the streaming giant Netflix, citing the potential for market dominance due to Netflix's already significant market share. [Read More](#)

Sidhu's CM Candidate Demand Sets Stage for Punjab Comeback

Navjot Singh Sidhu, the former Punjab Congress chief, may return to active politics, but his wife, Navjot Kaur Sidhu, has set a clear condition: the Congress party must declare him as its chief ministerial candidate in Punjab. [Read More](#)

Australia's World-First Social Media Ban for Under-16s

Australia is proceeding with its world-first ban preventing individuals under the age of 16 from accessing social media, an initiative aimed at safeguarding children from online dangers. The controversial legislation affects major digital platforms. [Read More](#)

Bridge Between Human Rights and Technical AI Standards

Council of Europe has positioned itself as the crucial link between human rights-based governance and AI technical standardisation. The Framework Convention on AI and human rights, stands as the first-ever international legally binding agreement. [Read More](#)

ICICI Bank's Chaotic KYC

ICICI Bank has crossed all limits of carelessness and customer harassment. Even after repeated complaints and wide public reporting, the bank continues to send me incessant KYC reminder emails. [Read More](#)

The Invisible Cuffs

It's a scenario that sounds like the plot of a political thriller: powerful leaders, accustomed to traversing the globe with impunity, are suddenly having their travel plans dictated by an international court. [Read More](#)

Cybersecurity App in India

India has ordered that all new smartphones manufactured or imported for use in the country must come pre-loaded with the state-run cybersecurity application, Sanchar Saathi. [Read More](#)

[Promote with Pathway.](#)

[Donate to RMN News](#)

THE UNREST news magazine is published by RMN News Service.

[Rakesh Raman](#)

Managing Editor

RMN News Service [www.rmnnnews.com]

463, DPS Apts., Plot No. 16, Sector 4, Dwarka, Phase I, New Delhi 110 078, India

WhatsApp / Mobile: 9810319059

Email: editor@rmnnnews.com

The Unrest | RMN News Magazine | December 16-31, 2025